

Estimation of Capsaicin by Spectrophotometry

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A new spectrophotometric method is reported for the estimation of capsaicin in capsicums and chillies. Capsaicin forms yellow colour complex with sodium nitrite and sodium tungstate under acidic condition and shows maximum absorbance at 430 nm and obeys Beers law for 2–35 μg capsaicin/ml.

THE pungency of chillies and capsicums are due to the presence of capsaicin and other related alkaloids. The traditional method of evaluating pungency by organoleptic method¹ in terms of Scoville heat units, has certain setbacks including rapid taster fatigue. Hence, much attention has been devoted to the development of newer physico-chemical methods for assessing the pungency. A wide spectrum of techniques, such as gc²⁻⁴, hplc⁵, tlc⁶, spectrofluorimetry⁷, spectrophotometry^{8,9} etc. have been reported. Most of the methods are time-consuming and involve elaborate procedures. A broad spectrum of chromogenic reagents have been reported to estimate capsaicin contents by spectrophotometry but each of these reagents have certain limitations, namely, VOCl_3 reagent⁹—the main disadvantages being the instability of the colour¹⁰, Folin—Denis reagent¹¹, Folin—Ciocalteu reagent¹², phosphomolybdic reagent, Gibbs reagent etc. are non-specific being redox reagents. Bajaj had earlier reported a method¹³ employing sodium nitrite under acidic condition in the presence of molybdate as catalyst. This method has certain drawbacks, namely, that the colour is stable only for 30 min, while the present investigation employing sodium nitrite reagent in the presence of sodium tungstate catalyst produces a colour stable for 3 h.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade. Solutions of 0.5 M sodium nitrite and 0.02 M sodium tungstate were prepared in double-distilled water. Standard capsaicin solution was prepared by dissolving capsaicin (E. Merck) (10 mg) in ethyl acetate and making up to 25 ml. A Britton—Robinson buffer solution of pH 2 was prepared. A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20 colorimeter was used. The clean up column was of glass packed with basic alumina (Brockman grade 1).

Extraction: Dry samples of 30 mesh powder was ground and 0.5 g powder was exactly weighed, extracted with acetone for 4 h in a soxhlet apparatus and filtered after cooling to room temperature. Acetone (5 \times 2 ml) was repeatedly added until the residue was free of pungency. Then the solvent was

evaporated on a water-bath (50°) and the residue was transferred into a 25 ml standard flask and diluted to volume with ethyl acetate and stored at 5°.

The above extract was directly used in the case of green chillies, but in the case of red chillies the extract was purified by column chromatography on alumina. Capsaicin was eluted with acetone—methanol—water mixture (75 : 25 : 2)¹⁴. The extraction was tried with various solvents, like methanol, acetone, ethyl acetate for one particular variety and the data in Table I indicate the efficiency of extraction with various solvents. Acetone extraction (refluxing, soxhlet apparatus) was found to be better than other solvent extractions.

TABLE I—EXTRACTION OF CAPSAICIN FROM GREEN CAPSICUM* USING DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Sl. no.	Extraction procedure	% Recovery of capsaicin g/g capsicum
1.	Aqueous methanol 50%	0.165
2.	Aqueous ethanol 50%	0.130
3.	Ethyl acetate	0.100
4.	Chloroform	0.125
5.	Acetone (shaking)	0.095
6.	Acetone (refluxing)	0.180
7.	Acetone (refluxing, soxhlet apparatus)	0.195

* Green capsicum variety being Sl. no. 3 mentioned in Table 8.

Identification of capsaicin by tlc: Tlc plates were prepared according to the standard procedure with silica gel and activated at 110° for 3 h and R_f values in various solvents were determined (Table 2).

TABLE 2—TLC STUDY OF CAPSAICIN

Sl. no.	Solvent	R_f
1.	Chloroform (running twice)	12
2.	Chloroform—Ethanol (96 : 4)	53
3.	Chloroform—Ethanol (97 : 3)	43
4.	Chloroform—Ethanol (98 : 2)	35
5.	Chloroform—Ethanol (99 : 1)	22
6.	Methanol—Acetic acid (98 : 2)	83
7.	Methanol—Benzene (96 : 4)	33
8.	Hexane—Ethyl ether (40 : 60)	11

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF CAPSAICIN CONTENT IN BOTH GREEN AND RED CAPSICUMS AND CHILLIES BY DIFFERENT METHODS

Samples Sl. no.	% of Capsaicin \pm S.D.		
	Present method ^a	Sodium nitrite—sodium molybdate method ^b	Folin—Ciocalteu method ^b
Green varieties			
1.	0.06 \pm 0.001 (9 000)	0.059 \pm 0.003 (8 850)	0.06 \pm 0.003 (9 000)
2.	0.16 \pm 0.001 (24 000)	0.16 \pm 0.004 (24 000)	0.15 \pm 0.002 (22 500)
3.	0.195 \pm 0.002 (29 250)	0.194 \pm 0.003 (29 100)	0.193 \pm 0.001 (28 950)
4.	0.24 \pm 0.002 (36 000)	0.23 \pm 0.003 (34 500)	0.24 \pm 0.002 (36 000)
5.	0.36 \pm 0.001 (54 000)	0.35 \pm 0.002 (52 500)	0.35 \pm 0.002 (52 500)
6.	0.42 \pm 0.003 (63 000)	0.42 \pm 0.001 (63 000)	0.42 \pm 0.001 (63 000)
Red varieties			
1.	0.09 \pm 0.002 (13 500)	0.085 \pm 0.001 (12 750)	0.085 \pm 0.003 (12 750)
2.	0.185 \pm 0.001 (27 750)	0.18 \pm 0.003 (27 000)	0.18 \pm 0.002 (27 000)
3.	0.235 \pm 0.002 (35 250)	0.23 \pm 0.003 (34 500)	0.23 \pm 0.004 (34 500)
4.	0.275 \pm 0.001 (41 250)	0.275 \pm 0.001 (41 250)	0.27 \pm 0.003 (40 500)
5.	0.39 \pm 0.001 (58 500)	0.385 \pm 0.001 (57 750)	0.38 \pm 0.002 (57 000)
6.	0.46 \pm 0.002 (69 000)	0.45 \pm 0.001 (67 500)	0.45 \pm 0.001 (67 500)

Figures in parentheses show the calculated values, taking pure capsaicin as 1.5×10^6 scoville heat units. ^a Mean of 5 replicates. ^b Mean of 4 replicates.

Estimation of capsaicin: Aliquots of standard capsaicin (0.05–0.5 ml) were pipetted out in a small beaker. The solvent was evaporated below 65° with a current of hot air. To each beaker, water (1 ml) and buffer solution (2 ml) were added followed by sodium nitrite (1 ml) and sodium tungstate (1 ml). The contents were mixed thoroughly and slightly warmed on a water-bath. After 15 min, 1 N NaOH (2 ml) was added and made up to a definite volume. Absorbance was read at 430 nm against a reagent blank.

Definite aliquots (1 or 3 ml in the case of low pungent chillies) of extracted samples of capsicum and chillies were taken and evaporated and the colour was developed following the above procedure. The concentrations were determined from the calibration curve and the capsaicin content was calculated (Table 3).

Results and Discussion

Sodium nitrite in the presence of sodium tungstate as a catalyst, reacts with capsaicin under acidic condition of pH 2, yielding a yellow colour. Finally, the solution is rendered alkaline by adding NaOH and an intense yellow colour is noticed.

Various concentrations of sodium nitrite—sodium tungstate were tried. Higher concentrations of reagent resulted in a slight decrease in absorbance. The optimum concentration of NaNO_2 was chosen as 0.5 M and that of sodium tungstate as 0.02 M. When the reagents were added to the sample solution at room temperature a yellow colour developed slowly but on warming over a water-bath (below 65°) the intensity of the colour was found to reach a maximum within 15 min. The solution showed maximum absorbance at 430 nm and molar absorptivity at 430 nm being 4.8×10^4 . Beer—

Lamberts law is obeyed in the range of 2–35 μg capsaicin/ml. Sandell sensitivity is 6.3×10^{-8} $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The intensity of colour remained unchanged even after 3 h. The method gave accurate and reproducible results. The determination of capsaicin content by the present method was compared with the earlier reported spectrophotometric method using sodium nitrite—sodium molybdate and Folin—Ciocalteu method. The results are in close agreement.

Estimation of capsaicin in tincture, ointments and food stuffs: The method was extended to the determination of capsaicin content in tinctures, ointments and food stuffs. Capsaicin from tinctures and ointments were extracted¹⁶. In the case of food stuffs, various brands of food stuffs (~0.5 g) were taken in a Soxhlet apparatus and refluxed for 4 h with acetone, followed by filtration through a glass wool. The filtrate was taken into a 25 ml standard flask and made up with acetone. A known amount of the solution was taken and poured into a column packed with basic alumina, and eluted with acetone—methanol—water (75 : 25 : 2) when capsaicin separated from other interfering materials. It was then directly taken for estimation following the previously mentioned methods. The results are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4—ESTIMATION OF CAPSAICIN CONTENT IN TINCTURES AND OINTMENTS OF CAPSAICIN AND SOME FOOD STUFFS BY PRESENT METHOD

Samples	% of capsaicin \pm S.D. ^a
<i>Tinctures</i>	
Tinctura capsici	0.049 \pm 0.002 (7 350)
Tinctura capsici fortior	0.040 \pm 0.001 (6 000)
<i>Ointments</i>	
Unguentum capsici	0.046 \pm 0.001 (6 900)
Unguentum capsici compositum	0.039 \pm 0.002 (5 850)
Unguentum capsici forte	0.031 \pm 0.002 (4 650)

(Table 4 contd.)

Food stuffs

Lalah's

Masala powder	0.028 ± 0.001 (4 200)
Sambar powder	0.023 ± 0.002 (3 450)

Ganeshram 777

Masala powder	0.028 ± 0.001 (3 900)
Sambar powder	0.023 ± 0.001 (3 450)

Singi's

Masala powder	0.024 ± 0.002 (3 600)
Sambar powder	0.022 ± 0.001 (3 300)

Figures in parentheses show the calculated values, taking pure capsaicin as 1.5×10^6 scoville heat units. * Mean of 3 replicates.

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